

Systematic Literature Review: Integrating Human Resource Management (HRM), Human Resource Development (HRD), and Industrial Relations (IR) in Fostering Sustainable Organizational Performance

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ABSTRACT

Perkembangan industri dan teknologi menuntut perusahaan memiliki SDM yang kompeten untuk mendukung pertumbuhan berkelanjutan. Penelitian ini menggunakan metode SLR (systematic literature review) dengan mengidentifikasi, mengevaluasi, dan menafsirkan seluruh penelitian yang relevan dengan topik. Tujuan penelitian ini adalah untuk menggali peran dari HRD, HRM, dan IR dalam membangun kinerja organisasi yang berkelanjutan. Hasil penelitian menunjukkan Integrasi HRM, HRD, dan IR mampu membentuk fondasi strategis bagi kinerja organisasi yang berkelanjutan. HRM menyediakan arah strategis dan inovasi, HRD mengembangkan kompetensi dan adaptabilitas, sedangkan IR menjaga stabilitas sosial dan produktivitas. Sinergi ketiganya menghasilkan organisasi yang kompetitif, tangguh, dan berkelanjutan, di mana keberlanjutan ditopang oleh kualitas tata kelola sumber daya manusia. Temuan penelitian mengintegrasikan HRM, HRD, dan IR berpotensi menjadi model manajemen SDM yang mendukung efisiensi sekaligus keberlanjutan sosial, inovasi, dan daya saing jangka panjang organisasi melalui implementasi dan penelitian lebih lanjut.

ABSTRAK

The advancement of industry and technology requires companies to possess competent human resources to support sustainable growth. This study employs a Systematic Literature Review (SLR) method to identify, evaluate, and interpret all relevant studies on the topic. The objective of this research is to explore the roles of HRD, HRM, and IR in building sustainable organizational performance. The findings indicate that the integration of HRM, HRD, and IR forms a strategic foundation for sustainable organizational performance. HRM provides strategic direction and innovation, HRD develops competencies and adaptability, while IR ensures social stability and productivity. The synergy among these three functions results in organizations that are competitive, resilient, and sustainable, where sustainability is supported by high-quality human resource governance. The findings suggest that integrating HRM, HRD, and IR has the potential to serve as a human resource management model that supports operational efficiency, social sustainability, innovation, and long-term organizational competitiveness, warranting further implementation and research.

INTRODUCTION

The rapid transformation of the global business landscape in the era of Industry 4.0 requires organizations to adapt to increasingly complex, competitive, and knowledge-driven environments (Rachman et al., 2024). The emergence of the ASEAN Economic Community has further intensified economic and business challenges across the region, demanding stronger economic stability and enhanced competitiveness at the global level. As one of the ASEAN member states entering a free-market arena, Indonesia is compelled to strengthen its readiness in facing heightened competition both in securing strategic resources and in producing high-quality products (Suryani, 2018). Consequently, organizations must implement human resource

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development initiatives that extend beyond short-term business objectives and instead emphasize long-term, sustainable growth (Gunawan, 2024).

Within this context, human resources (HR) serve as a critical determinant of organizational success due to their capacity to innovate, collaborate, and adapt to rapid change. This reality underscores the need for organizations to invest in HR innovation to safeguard competitiveness and ensure long-term sustainability amidst an increasingly volatile market environment (Firdaus & Kuswinarno, 2024). Consequently, human resource management and development practices have shifted from purely administrative functions toward becoming strategic instruments for building sustainable competitive advantage (Darma, 2024). The accelerated advancement of industry and technology has further amplified the demand for competent and motivated employees capable of supporting continuous organizational growth (Fareed et al., 2016). Ensuring sustainable growth requires organizations to cultivate a workforce equipped with the knowledge, skills, and competencies necessary to perform effectively in dynamic and highly complex environments (Fareed et al., 2016). Therefore, it is essential for organizations to implement HR development programs that not only pursue short-term business objectives but also intentionally foster long-term, sustainable organizational growth.

Human Resource Development (HRD) has become increasingly vital for ensuring organizational success in today's highly competitive and rapidly changing business environment (Norita & Oktariani, 2024). Well-designed HRD programs enhance employees' skills, knowledge, and attitudes, which in turn strengthen organizational productivity and competitiveness (Ariadna et al., 2023). Moreover, human resource development has been shown to exert a positive influence on employee performance (Aini et al., 2024). In recent years, the role of HRD within Indonesian organizations has undergone a significant transformation, shifting from an administrative function to a more strategic role in fostering employee development. This shift reflects a deeper recognition of HRD's contribution to overall organizational performance (Norita & Oktariani, 2024).

Human Resource Management (HRM), in parallel, has evolved into a comprehensive and strategic approach that positions human resources as the organization's primary asset and as a foundation for building sustainable competitive advantage (Armstrong, 2024). HRM encompasses the structures and processes that enable organizations to effectively recruit, train, and manage their workforce. Its strategic value extends beyond administrative functions, contributing to the creation of a productive and harmonious work environment that supports organizational sustainability (Dimitri et al., 2025). Overall, the strategic role of HRM is realized through coordinated efforts to cultivate a motivated, capable, and well-managed workforce. Effective HRM practices enhance employee performance and attitudes, strengthen interpersonal and team relationships, and foster a work culture that supports superior organizational outcomes (Firmansah & Gusti, 2025).

In addition, harmonious Industrial Relations (IR) between employees and employers serve as a critical determinant of organizational productivity and long-term sustainability. Industrial relations refer to interactions between employers and workers at national, regional, and organizational levels concerning socio-economic issues such as wage determination, working hours, and employment conditions (Aulia et al., 2025). An enabling organizational culture contributes to employee engagement, well-being, and productivity. Employee participation has been widely recognized as a key managerial tool for advancing organizational performance (Utami & Setiawardani, 2023). However, misalignment between employees and organizational expectations often poses challenges within industrial relations, affecting both performance and productivity (Agusalim, 2024). Strong relationships built on trust, open communication, and

mutual respect create a collaborative work environment that enhances employee engagement and retention (Aulia et al., 2025).

The integration of Human Resource Development (HRD), Human Resource Management (HRM), and Industrial Relations (IR) forms an interconnected system that collectively supports organizational effectiveness. HRD contributes to the establishment of a healthy and constructive work climate (Mahmud & Millad, 2025). HRM plays a crucial role in determining organizational success by optimizing workforce capabilities (Kabul, 2024). Meanwhile, industrial relations particularly through employee relations and welfare ensure harmonious interactions between management and employees while safeguarding their physical and psychological well-being (Aryanti & Dariyanti, 2025).

In practice, many organizations increasingly recognize that business strategies cannot succeed without effective human resource systems encompassing competency development, strategic alignment, and conducive employment relations. Employee participation in organizational activities is therefore essential (Agustini, 2019). These dynamics illustrate that HRD, HRM, and IR are interdependent elements that collectively shape sustainable organizational performance. HRD enhances individual and collective competencies; HRM provides strategic and managerial structures to leverage human potential; and IR ensures fairness, stability, and harmony in employment relationships. The integration of these three dimensions creates an organizational ecosystem that is innovative, adaptive, and competitively resilient.

Given these conditions, a systematic inquiry using a Systematic Literature Review (SLR) approach is required to map the roles and interactions of HRD, HRM, and IR in fostering sustainable organizational performance. The SLR approach enables a comprehensive and structured understanding of how the integration of Human Resource Management, Human Resource Development, and Industrial Relations collectively contributes to long-term organizational sustainability. This review is expected to provide deeper insights into the interrelationships among these constructs and their implications for organizational performance in the future.

METHODS

This study employs a Systematic Literature Review (SLR) approach. This method was selected to identify, evaluate, and comprehensively synthesize empirical research findings related to the integration of Human Resource Management (HRM), Human Resource Development (HRD), and Industrial Relations (IR) in fostering sustainable organizational performance. According to Resnawita and Hendrik (2023), the SLR methodology consists of several key stages, including:

Research Question

The first step in conducting an SLR is formulating the research questions, which involves defining the objectives of the review and determining the scope of analysis necessary to address those objectives. The research questions developed for this study are as follows:

RQ1: How does Human Resource Management (HRM) contribute to achieving sustainable organizational performance?

RQ2: In what ways does Human Resource Development (HRD) enhance employee competencies, innovation capacity, and adaptability to support sustainable organizational performance?

RQ3: How does a harmonious system of Industrial Relations (IR) influence organizational productivity and sustainable performance?

Searching Literature

The next stage involves conducting a systematic search for scholarly literature through reputable academic databases to obtain sources that are relevant to the predefined research questions. This activity aims to gather comprehensive and credible references that can adequately support the synthesis process. In this study, the literature search was carried out using the ScienceDirect database (<https://www.sciencedirect.com/>)

The keywords used in the search process included: ("human resource management" OR "HRM") AND ("human resource development" OR "HRD") AND ("industrial relations" OR "employment relations") AND ("integration" OR "collaboration") AND ("organizational performance")

Inclusion and Exclusion Criteria

The article selection process was conducted using strict eligibility criteria to ensure the relevance and quality of the studies included in the review. The inclusion and exclusion criteria are outlined as follows:

Criteria	Inclusion	Exclusion
Searching	Articles published by Elsevier (ScienceDirect)	Articles not published by Elsevier (ScienceDirect)
Main Variables	Studies examining HRM, HRD, IR, and organizational performance	Studies that do not include HRM, HRD, IR, or organizational performance
Publication Range	Articles published between 2010 and 2025	Articles published before 2010
Accessibility	Articles available in full-text format	Articles not available in full-text format

Quality assessment

This stage involves assessing the methodological rigor and informational quality of the articles selected in the previous steps. The quality assessment criteria established for this review are described as follows:

QA1: Does the study's central focus align with the theme of integrating HRM, HRD, and IR within the context of sustainable organizational performance?

QA2: Are the research objectives clearly articulated and consistent with the results presented in the article?

QA3: Are the findings and discussion sections clearly presented, and do they demonstrate a coherent connection to the themes of HRM, HRD, IR, and organizational performance?

Data collection

The scope of data collection begins with gathering relevant literature, selecting journal articles that meet the established inclusion criteria, and extracting essential information from the eligible studies. The data collection process in this review consisted of the following steps:

1). Primary Data

Primary data refer to information obtained directly from original sources. In this study, the primary data collection process involved several stages, including:

- a. **Observation**, conducted through direct examination of sources available on the ScienceDirect platform <https://www.sciencedirect.com/>

- b. Literature Review, carried out by reviewing and analyzing previously published, relevant journal articles obtained exclusively from ScienceDirect to strengthen the evidence base of the study.
- c. Documentation, involving the systematic storage and organization of collected data in Google Drive, followed by the integration and management of these documents using Mendeley reference management software.

2). Secondary Data

Secondary data were obtained from journal articles that had been previously published. This category includes data that already exist and were not collected directly by the researcher. Secondary data in this review comprise documented research findings sourced from reputable academic publications.

Data analysis

The data analysis process consists of a series of systematic steps designed to transform raw data into meaningful, interpretable information. The collected literature was examined with the intention of identifying patterns, extracting key insights, and validating the relationships proposed in the research questions. The analytical framework used in this study focused on the following aspects:

- a. HRM Contribution (RQ1): Does the article explain how Human Resource Management (HRM) contributes to achieving sustainable organizational performance?
- b. HRD Contribution (RQ2): Does the article describe the extent to which Human Resource Development (HRD) enhances sustainable organizational performance?
- c. IR Contribution (RQ3): Does the article provide an explanation of how Industrial Relations (IR) influence sustainable organizational performance?

Reporting

The final stage, reporting, involves presenting the research findings in a systematic and comprehensive manner. The conclusions are formulated based on the synthesized evidence, accompanied by recommendations relevant to organizational stakeholders. The outcomes of this review are expected to be disseminated through academic journals or conferences to contribute meaningfully to the body of knowledge in the field of business and education.

RESULT AND DISCUSSION

Research Question

This study focuses on examining the roles of Human Resource Management (HRM), Human Resource Development (HRD), and Industrial Relations (IR) in fostering sustainable organizational performance.

Searching Literature

The literature search conducted through ScienceDirect identified a total of 92 articles based on the specified keywords ("human resource management" OR "HRM") AND ("human resource development" OR "HRD") AND ("industrial relations" OR "employment relations") AND ("integration" OR "collaboration") AND ("organizational performance")

Figure 1. Searching Literature

Following the literature search process, a total of 62 journals were identified as relevant to the research theme. These articles were then subjected to the inclusion and exclusion assessment criteria for further screening.

The results of the inclusion and exclusion assessment are as follows:

Criteria	Inclusion	Result
Searching	Articles published by Elsevier (ScienceDirect)	A total of 62 articles matched the topic
Main Variables	Studies examining HRM, HRD, IR, and organizational performance	A total of 41 articles met this requirement
Publication Range	Articles published between 2010 and 2025	A total of 28 articles fit within the range
Accessibility	Articles available in full-text format	A total of 18 articles were fully accessible

Figure 2. Articles matched the topic

Figure 3. Articles met this requirement

Figure 4. articles fit within the range

Figure 5. articles were fully accessible

Quality Assessment Stage

The selection process through inclusion and exclusion criteria resulted in 18 eligible articles. Subsequently, the quality-assessment stage identified 9 articles that met the required standards and were deemed suitable to be used as high-quality references.

No	Article	QA1	QA2	QA3
1	Banmairuoy, W., Kritjaroen, T., & Homsombat, W. (2022). The effect of knowledge-oriented leadership and human resource development on sustainable competitive advantage through organizational innovation's component factors: Evidence from Thailand's new S-curve industries. <i>Asia Pacific Management Review</i> , 27(3), 200-209.	√	√	√
2	Kesti, M. (2012). Organization human resources development connection to business performance. <i>Procedia economics and finance</i> , 2, 257-264.	√	√	√
3	Adnan, Z., Abdullah, H. S., & Ahmad, J. (2016). Assessing the moderating effect of competition intensity on HRM practices and organizational performance link: The experience of Malaysian R&D companies. <i>Procedia Economics and Finance</i> , 35, 462-467	√	√	√
4	Keltu, T. T. (2024). The effect of human resource development practice on employee performance with the mediating role of job satisfaction among Mizan Tepi University's academic staff in Southwestern Ethiopia. <i>Heliyon</i> , 10(8).	√	√	√
5	Gurbuz, S., & Mert, I. S. (2011). Impact of the strategic human resource management on organizational performance: Evidence from Turkey. <i>The International Journal of Human Resource Management</i> , 22(8), 1803-1822.	√	√	√
6	Kokkaew, N., Jokkaw, N., Peansupap, V., & Wipulanusat, W. (2022). Impacts of human resource management and knowledge management on non-financial organizational performance: Evidence of Thai infrastructure construction firms. <i>Ain Shams Engineering Journal</i> , 13(6), 101750.	√	√	√
7	Aman-Ullah, A., Mehmood, W., Amin, S., & Abbas, Y. A. (2022). Human capital and organizational performance: A moderation	√	√	√

	study through innovative leadership. <i>Journal of innovation & knowledge</i> , 7(4), 100261.			
8	Hu, X., Rahman, H., Nguyenthi, Y., & Li, M. (2024). Internationalization of Cambodia garment factories' industrial relations governance. <i>Asian Journal of Social Science</i> , 52(1), 44-50.	√	√	√
9	Godino, A., & Molina, O. (2022). The industrial relations chameleon: collective bargaining in the facility management business. <i>Employee Relations: The International Journal</i> , 44(7), 1-18.	√	√	√

Result

RQ1: How does Human Resource Management (HRM) contribute to achieving sustainable organizational performance?

In the context of modern management, Human Resource Management (HRM) is increasingly recognized as a decisive factor in enabling organizations to achieve long-term performance objectives. The paradigm shift from an administrative view of human resource management toward a strategic orientation requires organizations to position people as the central drivers of innovation, adaptability, and sustainability. HRM is no longer confined to managing the workforce; it functions as a strategic partner responsible for aligning individual potential with organizational vision and strategy. This shift underscores the importance of integrating competency development, dynamic organizational culture, and adaptive management systems capable of responding to environmental uncertainties.

The findings of Gurbuz and Mert (2011) reinforce this perspective by demonstrating that strategic HRM practices characterized by vertical alignment between HR goals and business strategies, and horizontal integration across HR functions positively influence organizational performance in the Turkish context. Organizations adopting strategic HRM (SHRM) tend to experience higher employee satisfaction and productivity because HR practices are fully synchronized with organizational needs. Thus, HRM contributes to sustainable performance by embedding human resource strategies into long-term corporate planning rather than limiting its role to administrative tasks such as recruitment or compensation.

Complementing these insights, Kokkaew et al. (2022) provide empirical evidence that HRM exerts a direct influence on knowledge management (KM) and non-financial organizational performance within Thailand's infrastructure construction sector. Their findings emphasize that HRM plays a vital role in strengthening organizational learning capacity and knowledge management processes, ultimately enhancing the learning and growth dimension of sustainable performance. In this context, HRM does not merely shape a competent workforce but also establishes mechanisms that foster knowledge transfer, innovation, and cross-functional collaboration. Consequently, HRM becomes a bridge between talent management and the creation of adaptive learning organizations capable of navigating rapid changes in the business environment.

Further reinforcing the strategic importance of HRM, Attia et al. (2022) highlight human capital as the core determinant of organizational performance. The capabilities, knowledge, and skills of employees significantly affect organizational outcomes, while innovative leadership acts as a moderating factor that strengthens the relationship between human capital knowledge and performance. This suggests that HRM strategies centered on human capital development must be

integrated with leadership approaches that stimulate innovation to achieve sustained performance improvements. The success of HRM in enhancing organizational performance hinges on its ability to coordinate knowledge management, leadership effectiveness, and workforce competencies.

Taken together, these findings illustrate that HRM serves as a strategic foundation for building sustainable organizational performance through three key dimensions: strategic alignment, knowledge- and innovation-driven HRM, and human capital development strengthened by innovative leadership. HRM that is vertically integrated with business strategy and horizontally synchronized across internal functions enhances the efficiency and effectiveness of human resource operations, ensuring that all HR activities support long-term organizational objectives. Moreover, HRM facilitates organizational learning, stimulates innovation, and manages knowledge as a strategic asset, thereby fostering a competitive and adaptive learning culture. By advancing employees' skills, competencies, and knowledge combined with leadership that encourages creativity and continuous improvement HRM strengthens the organization's human capital base and long-term competitive advantage.

Overall, this systematic review confirms that HRM contributes substantially to sustainable organizational performance by creating an integrated, knowledge-based, and innovation-oriented human resource system. Such a system positions the workforce not merely as an administrative component but as a strategic asset that drives growth, learning, and sustainability in an increasingly dynamic global environment.

RQ2: In what ways does Human Resource Development (HRD) enhance employee competencies, innovation capacity, and adaptability to support sustainable organizational performance?

Based on the synthesis of the reviewed literature, Human Resource Development (HRD) plays a strategic role in enhancing employee competencies, fostering innovation, and strengthening adaptive capabilities as the foundation of sustainable organizational performance, even though its influence is not always direct. The findings of Banmairuoy et al. (2022) reveal that HRD does not exert a significant direct effect on sustainable competitive advantage; however, it contributes indirectly through organizational innovation. This indicates that the effectiveness of HRD depends strongly on its ability to cultivate an organizational culture that supports creativity, knowledge-sharing, and continuous learning. Accordingly, HRD functions as a catalyst linking human capital development, innovation-oriented leadership, and the organization's capacity to adapt to industrial change.

Kesti (2012) emphasizes the importance of HRD in shaping Quality of Working Life (QWL) and collective competence in the workplace. Effective HRD initiatives must target improvements in core human capabilities such as leadership, team culture, and process efficiency because these elements significantly drive productivity and innovation. When integrated with QWL, HRD not only enhances employee well-being but also strengthens the organization's resilience in responding to shifts in business strategies and dynamic work environments. Adnana et al. (2016) provide further evidence that organizational failure to integrate HRD with external environmental demands weakens its impact on performance outcomes. Research and development firms in Malaysia that remain focused on administrative HRD functions such as routine training and reward systems struggle to leverage HRD as a strategic instrument in navigating competitive pressures and innovation challenges.

Their findings highlight that effective HRD must be contextually designed, aligned with environmental dynamics, and directed toward building innovative capabilities and organizational flexibility. Complementing these insights, Keltu (2024) demonstrates that HRD

practices such as training and development, teamwork, counseling, and succession planning significantly influence employee performance and job satisfaction, both directly and indirectly. Job satisfaction acts as a mediating variable that strengthens the relationship between HRD and individual as well as organizational performance. This suggests that HRD initiatives oriented toward career development and psychological well-being increase employee commitment, productivity, and long-term organizational sustainability.

Overall, the synthesized findings illustrate that HRD holds a complex and multidimensional role in advancing sustainable organizational performance. HRD is not merely an administrative function; it is a strategic mechanism that links individual development, organizational innovation, and adaptive responses to external change. Its effectiveness is maximized when integrated with knowledge-based leadership, innovation strategies, collective competence development, quality of working life, and psychological well-being. Through this integration, HRD serves as a bridge between human development and organizational sustainability, ensuring that employees are not only technically competent but also innovative, adaptive, and competitively positioned for long-term success.

RQ3: How does a harmonious system of Industrial Relations (IR) influence organizational productivity and sustainable performance?

Following the discussion on the role of Human Resource Management (HRM) in strengthening individual capabilities and long-term performance, the focus now shifts to the collective dimension Industrial Relations (IR). While HRM primarily concerns individual employment relationships, IR regulates the broader interactions among management, workers (including unions), and government within a tripartite governance system. The balance and harmony within these relationships are essential; even when HRM practices are well-developed, industrial conflict has the potential to disrupt stability and hinder operational continuity. Thus, harmonious IR is a foundational element for ensuring sustained productivity and consistent organizational performance over the long term.

Hu et al. (2024) demonstrate that in Cambodia's garment sector, the industrial relations system has undergone structural transformation driven by deeper integration into the global economy. Employment relations are no longer governed solely by traditional tripartite mechanisms involving the state, employers, and workers; instead, they are increasingly shaped by global actors such as multinational corporations, international organizations, and stakeholders from importing and exporting countries. These actors influence IR through four key mechanisms: political authority, economic power, public mobilization, and professional training. As a result, modern IR governance operates within a complex global network where labor standards, productivity, and sustainability are influenced by international demands. Although this global integration offers opportunities to enhance worker skills and organizational efficiency through training and the adoption of international standards, dependence on external forces may also constrain the autonomy of local unions and weaken their bargaining power. The central challenge for sustainable IR in this globalized context is maintaining equilibrium between local interests and global pressures ensuring productivity gains without compromising worker welfare.

Complementing this perspective, Godino and Molina (2022) highlight how industrial relations in the Facility Management (FM) sector display a "chameleon-like" ability to adapt to different national institutional environments. Their findings reveal that the effectiveness of IR is shaped not only by industry maturity but more critically by the strength of collective bargaining institutions within each country. Nations with robust IR structures tend to uphold labor

standards and prevent wage-dumping practices. Conversely, in countries with decentralized bargaining systems, union power is often diluted, enabling firms to reduce labor standards in pursuit of cost efficiency. Harmonious IR does not imply the absence of conflict; rather, it reflects the presence of fair, institutionalized, and adaptive negotiation mechanisms capable of managing disputes constructively. In this context, sectoral collective bargaining emerges as a crucial instrument for balancing economic objectives with workers' rights, ultimately contributing to sustainable organizational performance by enhancing employee loyalty, trust, and productivity.

CONCLUSION

The systematic review demonstrates that the integration of Human Resource Management (HRM), Human Resource Development (HRD), and Industrial Relations (IR) constitutes a strategic foundation for building sustainable organizational performance. These three pillars operate as an interconnected system: HRM aligns human capital with long-term business strategies, HRD strengthens workforce capabilities and innovation potential, and IR ensures social stability and productivity through equitable and harmonious employment relations.

First, HRM contributes substantially to organizational sustainability by embedding strategic HR practices into the company's long-term objectives. A strategic HRM approach fosters a balance between efficiency and innovation through competency development, knowledge management, and visionary leadership. HRM has evolved beyond administrative functions to become a strategic partner that generates value by fostering learning organizations and cultivating adaptive cultures responsive to global dynamics.

Second, HRD serves as a catalyst for organizational learning, innovation, and adaptability. Although its effects on sustainable performance are not always direct, HRD contributes through the development of collective competencies, the enhancement of quality of working life, and the reinforcement of organizational cultures that support creativity. The effectiveness of HRD depends on its integration with innovation-oriented strategies and knowledge-based leadership. When HRD extends beyond formal training to encompass critical-thinking skills, flexibility, and psychological well-being, organizations become more resilient and capable of navigating a disruptive business environment.

Third, harmonious IR functions as a prerequisite for sustainable organizational performance by maintaining stable relationships among employees, management, and external stakeholders. Empirical findings indicate that well-institutionalized IR systems effectively balance economic efficiency with social equity. Harmonious IR does not imply the absence of conflict, but rather the presence of fair, structured, and adaptive mechanisms for dialogue and negotiation. In the context of globalization, robust IR enables organizations to sustain productivity and social legitimacy through ethical and inclusive labor practices.

Overall, the integration of HRM, HRD, and IR creates a mutually reinforcing ecosystem of human resource governance. HRM provides strategic alignment, HRD nurtures competence and innovation, and IR safeguards social stability and productivity. Their synergy produces organizations that are not only competitively superior but also resilient, adaptive, and sustainable. Thus, long-term organizational sustainability is shaped not merely by economic capital but by the quality of human resource governance capable of harmonizing strategic, humanistic, and social dimensions within a unified sustainability framework.

RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the synthesis of the nine selected articles, several relevant recommendations can be proposed for organizational practitioners, policymakers, and future researchers.

1. For Organizational Practitioners and Managers

Organizations should adopt an integrative approach that aligns HRM, HRD, and IR as a unified strategic system. HRM must evolve into a true strategic partner in long-term business planning rather than functioning merely as an administrative unit. HRM practices oriented toward knowledge-based management and innovation should be strengthened through robust performance management systems, the development of innovative leadership, and the cultivation of an organizational culture that supports continuous learning and adaptive capability.

2. For HRD Departments and Human Capital Developers

The HRD function should be contextually designed to respond effectively to shifts in the business environment and advances in technology. Training programs must extend beyond technical skill enhancement to include the development of soft skills, critical thinking, creativity, and psychological well-being. Integrating HRD initiatives with quality of working life (QWL) and organizational innovation strategies can produce a workforce that is more adaptive, innovative, and highly committed to long-term organizational sustainability.

3. For Government and Labor Policy Makers

Governments should strengthen regulatory frameworks that promote fair and harmonious industrial relations. Labor policies must ensure the protection of workers' rights while allowing sufficient flexibility for firms to innovate and enhance productivity. Expanding sectoral, institutionalized collective bargaining mechanisms is essential for maintaining an equitable balance between economic priorities, social welfare, and long-term sustainability.

4. For Labor Unions and Social Stakeholders

Labor unions are encouraged to strengthen their negotiation capacity through data-driven strategies, knowledge enhancement, and strategic partnerships so they can play an active role in balancing worker welfare with organizational performance. In an era of globalization, it is essential for unions to build cross-sectoral and transnational collaborative networks to reinforce bargaining power and prevent wage-dumping practices.

5. For Future Researchers

Future research is encouraged to explore the integrated HRM, HRD, and IR model more extensively through both quantitative and qualitative approaches. Emerging variables such as transformational leadership, digital HRM systems, employee well-being, and organizational resilience may be incorporated to broaden the understanding of the determinants of sustainable organizational performance. Comparative studies across industries or countries could also offer deeper insights into how the effectiveness of this triad varies across different cultural contexts and institutional frameworks.

With deeper implementation and continued scholarly exploration, the integration of HRM, HRD, and IR holds the potential to evolve into a human resource management model that is not only efficiency-oriented, but also grounded in social sustainability, innovation, and long-term organizational competitiveness.

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